

MULTISCALE MODEL BASED ON A FINITE FRACTURE APPROACH FOR THE PREDICTION ON DAMAGE IN LAMINATE COMPOSITES

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1 Introduction

The use of laminate CRFP composites to manufacture large structures, such as aeronautical or wind turbines for instance, has drastically increased over the past few years. The design improvement of such structures strongly depends on the capabilities to model the damage mechanisms of this kind of material. The multiscale nature of these materials leads to complex and coupled damage mechanisms (in-plane failure and delamination). Moreover, the threshold and the kinetic of some damage mechanisms are function of the stacking sequence and the thickness of the plies [1]. The aim of this paper is to propose a model, based on physical damage mechanisms, to describe the damageable behavior up to the final failure of laminated composites.

2 Finite fracture mechanics based model

The failure mechanisms are described using a coupled criterion (i) a stress criterion to describe the onset of failure and (ii) an energetic criterion to describe the propagation of the failure.

Two kinds of mechanism are distinguished: the catastrophic failure mechanisms and the progressive transverse cracking modeling.

Fibers failures (tension and compression) and the transverse compression failure are considered as catastrophic (see table 1). For each failure mode, the associated catastrophic behavior is described by a bilinear law (see figure 1) where $\sigma_a^{i\mp}$ is the threshold of failure determined thanks to failure criterion $f^{i\mp}$ given in table 1. $\varepsilon_c^{i\mp}$ is the critical strain at failure determined thanks the energetic criterion :

$$\frac{1}{2} \sigma_a^{i\mp} \varepsilon_c^{i\mp} * Lwt = G_c^{i\mp} * S_f^{i\mp}$$

Where L,w,t are given by the geometry of the finite element (see figure 1), $G_c^{i\mp}$ and $S_f^{i\mp}$ are respectively the toughness and the fracture surface associated to the failure mode. The geometry of the finite element being introduce in this kind formulation, already used in [1], the results are not a function of the mesh size.

Fig. 1. Shape of the behavior associated to the catastrophic failure modes

Tension fiber failure	
	$f^{1+} = \left(\frac{\langle \sigma_{11} \rangle_+}{X_t} \right)^2$ $S_f^{1+} = t * L$
Compression fiber failure	
	$f^{1-} = \left(\frac{\langle \sigma_{11} \rangle_+}{X_c} \right)^2$ $S_f^{1-} = t * L$
Compression interf-fiber failure	
	$f^{2-} = \left(\frac{\langle \sigma_{22} \rangle_-}{Y_c} \right)^2 + \left(\frac{\langle \sigma_{12} \rangle_+}{S_c} \right)^2$ $S_f^{2-} = t * w$

Tab. 1 Catastrophic failure modes. Xt and Xc are respectively the tension and compression strength in fiber direction. Yc is the compression failure strength in transverse direction.

The progressive transverse cracking is mainly described by a physical damage variable $\bar{\rho}$ (the normalized crack density, i.e. the crack density multiplied by the thickness of the considered ply).

The threshold of $\bar{\rho}$ is described by

$$f^{2+} = \left(\frac{\langle \sigma_{22} \rangle_+}{Y_t} \right)^2 + \left(\frac{\langle \sigma_{12} \rangle_+}{S_c} \right)^2$$

Where Y_t and S_c are respectively the “*in-situ*” transverse tension strength and the shear strength [1].

The kinetic is described by an energetic criterion based on the variation of energy between a state at time t (with N crack of unitary surface S_f^{2+}) and the state at time $t+\Delta t$ (with $N+\Delta N$ crack of unitary surface S_f^{2+}). This variation of energy must be greater than the energy necessary to create the cracks [2]

$$(W(t + \Delta t) - W(t)) * L * w * t = G_c^m * \Delta N * L * w$$

Introducing in this equation the variation of the normalized crack density, one obtained

$$\Delta W = G_c^m \frac{\Delta \bar{\rho}}{t}$$

Where G_c^m is the toughness (function of the mode mixity). ΔW is a function of $\bar{\rho}$ and is computed thanks to a multiscale approach [3].

The identification procedure is based on classical tension on compression tests (for the strength) and fracture mechanics tests (for the toughness). The only non-normalized test is the CT test used to identify the toughness in fiber direction.

Preliminary results

The comparison between the experimental results and the ones obtained by the model in term of the crack density evolution as a function of the load is given in figure 2. Two kinds of materials are investigated (Carbon/Epoxy and Glass/Epoxy). Different laminates ($[0,90_n,0]$ with $n=1,2,4,6$ and $[0,+/-\theta_4,0_{1/2}]_s$ with $\theta=90, 70,55$) are studied. The results permit to show that the model permits (i) to reproduce the influence of the ply thickness on the threshold of damage and (ii) to describe in a correct

way the evolution of the crack density as a function of the ply angle.

In the final paper, this model will be compared o,n other materials and will be applied to structural cases (open-hole plates).

(a)

(b)

Fig. 1. Comparison between experimental and numerical results for C/epoxy laminates [3] and G/epoxy laminates [4]

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